

Community Support As A Buffer Against Economic Stress: Strengthening Mental Health Resilience Among Nigerians

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ABSTRACT: Community support plays an important role in buffering the adverse effects of economic stress on mental health among Nigerians. This paper explores the dynamics of traditional support systems, including family networks, age grades, religious institutions, and communal ties, and their contributions to mental health resilience amidst economic challenges. Drawing on Resilience and Ecological Systems Theories, the paper illuminates the mechanisms through which community support mitigates the psychological impacts. In rural Nigeria, the communitarian lifestyle deeply ingrained in the culture, spiritual beliefs and spiritual leaders often serve as the first line of support for mental health issues. The implications of these suggest the need for incorporating community structures into national mental health policies, investing in community-driven initiatives, and conducting further research on the effectiveness of community-based mental health strategies. By leveraging the inherent strengths of rural communities and integrating them with formal mental health services, Nigeria can develop a comprehensive approach to promoting mental well-being amidst economic adversity.

Keywords: Community Support, Economic Stress, Mental Health, Resilience, Nigeria

I. INTRODUCTION

At the height of the COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria, a man was arrested by the security agencies for breaching the lockdown order. The man pulled off his clothes in full view of everyone on the street, stating that the lockdown was adversely affecting his family as he had not been able to feed his family for some time. This man's reaction demonstrates that economic challenges can indeed change the thought process of any man (Onyemaechi et al., 2018). This is not an uncommon sight in Nigeria, especially in low-income regions where the dangerous impact of economic challenges on the mental health of individuals and families is felt more regularly than in other regions. It used to be that people in. However, it seems that the buck has also shifted to

urban areas, where employment opportunities have become rare. Those who are employed complain that the economic stress is too heavy for them to bear (Onyemaechi, 2025). Nigerians are currently grappling with high unemployment rates and economic instability. The psychological toll of these factors can be severe. There is no dearth of literature on the interplay between economic stressors and mental health. Evidence from the literature reveals a concerning trend: as economic conditions get worse, the rate of depression, anxiety, and other mental health disorders increases. Many people in Nigeria have faced or are facing hopelessness and despair due to the harsh realities of economic hardship (Ezeokana et al., 2017). The hopelessness and despair worsen the vulnerability of the already suffering population.

These challenges, notwithstanding, certain inherent strengths are activated in the communities and act as buffers against economic stress. These strengths are systems that help cultivate resilience. They include family networks, religious institutions, and communal ties. Their role in promoting mental health resilience among individuals facing adversity cannot be overstated. These traditional systems have their foundation in the communitarian lifestyle of the Africans as opposed to the individualistic lifestyle of the Westerners. "I am because we are; and since we are, therefore I am," is an axiom attributed to John Mbiti, which summarizes the substance of African communitarian philosophy and has significant implications for understanding personhood and social existence for the Africans (Adeate, 2023). It emphasizes that one's identity is shaped by relationships and social context, demonstrating the deep interconnectedness between individuals and their communities (Jennings, 2023). These traditional systems that point to our interconnectedness are not merely sources of social interaction; they are crucial frameworks that provide emotional, spiritual, and practical support during times of crisis. One of the many things learnt from communitarian lifestyle as Africans is that community support can significantly mitigate the adverse effects of economic stress on mental health (Onyemaechi, Nwagbo and Tingri, 2022). This paper explores the dynamics of community support in Nigeria, focusing on how these traditional support systems contribute to mental health resilience amidst economic challenges. The paper draws on existing literature and theoretical frameworks such as Resilience Theory, Social Support Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory to illuminate the mechanisms through which community support serves as a buffer against the psychological impacts of economic stress. It will become clearer that fostering mental health resilience is not solely the responsibility of mental health practitioners or policymakers; it demands a collective effort that recognizes and amplifies the power of community support. When these relationships are being understood better, appreciation of leveraging on community strengths to address mental health challenges among the population will be accepted by all. This understanding is for developing effective interventions that align with the cultural and social realities of the Nigerian population ultimately leading to improved mental health outcomes in challenging times.

Several reasons make addressing mental health in economically stressed environments crucial. In the first place, economic stress often leads to increased rates of mental health disorders, including anxiety, depression, and substance. In communities with high rates, individuals may face chronic stressors such as unemployment and uncertainty about the future. These factors worsen mental health issues, leading to a cycle of poverty and poor mental health that is difficult to break. Also, the implications of untreated mental health issues go beyond the individual level and affect families and communities in general. Mental health disorders can impair an individual's ability to function effectively in daily life (Achebe & Onyemaechi, 2023). This hinders their capacity to work, care for family members, and engage in social activities. This is a dysfunction that can strain familial relationships, decrease community cohesion, and further worsen the challenges faced by those living in economically disadvantaged situations. When an individual neglects their mental health, the domino effects of neglect can create a pervasive atmosphere of despair, reducing community resilience and making efforts to address economic challenges complicated. Additionally, it is vital to address mental health for the promotion of overall community well-being. The community is made up of different families, and these families are made up of individuals. Healthy individuals contribute to more robust, more productive communities. When prioritizing mental health in economically stressed environments, we improve individual well-being and foster community resilience. Individuals can better cope with stress, enhance their problem-solving abilities, and participate actively in community life with good integration of mental health support initiatives opined Okonkwo et al (2023). Finally, existing community support systems can be an effective strategy for promoting mental well-being, where mental health resources are often limited. Communal ties and social networks can serve as crucial sources of support, enabling individuals to handle economic stressors more effectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

a) Economic Stress and Mental Health

Studies have been conducted in various countries, including Nigeria with the results consistently showing a clear link between economic stress and adverse mental health outcomes (Onyemaechi et al., 2018). Economic stress is characterized by financial crises, unemployment, and socioeconomic instability. This significantly contributes to psychological distress. In Nigeria, research was conducted to reveal a high prevalence of financial crises and socioeconomic stressors, which are strongly associated with increased stress levels and anxiety (Chekwubechukwu, 2021, Anazonwu, et.al 2016). This is not different from global trends, as studies from other countries indicate similar patterns. For instance, in Spain and Portugal, economic hardship was identified as a significant predictor of psychological distress among vulnerable populations. Ayala-Nunes et al. (2017) revealed in a study that individuals facing severe economic difficulties experienced higher levels of anxiety and depression. In the same way, during the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States, economic-related anticipatory stress was shown to have a strong association with mental health challenges, especially depression and anxiety (Farina et al., 2023). All these studies emphasize the significant impact of economic uncertainty on mental well-being across diverse settings. A similar was also conducted in South Africa, this time focusing on adolescents. In that study, socioeconomic adversity was found to increase adolescents' vulnerability to stress, which in turn negatively affects their mental health. Harrison et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of recognizing how poverty and economic challenges worsen mental health issues in young people, making them more susceptible to psychological distress. These study findings reflect the global trend linking economic challenges to adverse mental health outcomes.

Financial hardship, economic decline and perceived financial stress are significant predictors of psychological distress, including symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress (Jesus et al., 2016; Hassan et al., 2021; Viseu et al., 2018, Anazonwu,et. al 2016). The relationship between economic stressors and mental health is particularly pronounced during periods of economic crisis, such as the 2008 economic meltdown (Ayala-Nunes et al., 2017; Viseu et al., 2018). Mccloud & Bann (2019) observed that subjective measures of financial stress, such as experiences of financial difficulties and debt worry, show a more consistent relationship with poor mental health among higher education students in the UK. It is interesting to note that several studies have identified potential buffers that can mitigate the negative impact of economic stress on mental health. The research conducted by Chekwubechukwu (2021) demonstrated that religious activities and doctrinal teachings provide some level of psychological relief during periods of economic hardship. Globally, social support networks and state policies with strong social safety nets have also been found to mitigate the effects of financial hardship on mental health. For instance, Ayala-Nunes et al. (2017) and Farina et al. (2023) suggest that stronger social support systems and state interventions can be crucial in buffering mental health challenges during economic crises. It is important to note, however, that the effectiveness of these buffers can vary depending on the severity of economic stress and the specific population studies. In regions with weaker social safety nets, such as many low-income and middle-income countries, the buffering capacity of social support systems may be limited.

b) The Role of Social Support Systems

Social support systems are crucial for maintaining psychological well-being and mental health outcomes. The literature shows that social ties can influence mental health through two models, referred to as the main effect model and the buffering model (Kawachi, 2001). These support systems can prevent depression, reduce psychological distress, and facilitate access to care and services, especially for vulnerable populations (Guruge et al., 2015, Onyemaechi,et.al 2023). However, it is worth noting that the impact of social support is not uniform across different groups in society. There is a higher prevalence of psychological distress among women compared to men, which may be due to the gender differences in deriving support from social support networks (Onyemaechi, Aroyewun &Ifeagwazi,2017; Kawachi, 2001). Moreover, social connections can paradoxically increase mental illness symptoms among women with insufficient resources, especially if the connections involve the role of providing social support to others (Kawachi, 2001). Wright (2016) highlights the importance of online social support networks. These can interact with face-to-face support networks to influence physical and psychological health outcomes. Sadiq (2023) conducted a recent study in Iraq in which it was demonstrated that online social support networks significantly contributed to mitigating psychological distress among women in the post-pandemic period, especially for those in remote or socially conservative areas with limited access to traditional support systems. However, it is worth noting that social support can have both positive and negative dimensions, and social networks can also serve as sources of distress and conflict (Guruge et al., 2015, Uzoma,et.al 2021).

Research has consistently demonstrated that social support provided through networks of social relationships has a protective effect on both physical and mental health (Stansfeld & Khatib, 2011). These networks can offer direct health benefits and buffer the impact of individual adversity, including economic hardship. Reeskens & Vandecasteele (2016) observed that social networks, religiosity, and confidence in politics can cushion the negative impact of economic strain on happiness. However, these protective measures are only effective when the strength of the welfare state is considered. In countries with lower levels of social expenditure, the positive effect of social networks and confidence in politics is stronger (Okoye, Onyemaechi & Umenweke, 2017). This suggests that a strong welfare system can even replace these protective buffers' role in society.

In the context of Nigeria, evidence abounds in the literature that traditional support systems such as social support networks are crucial in different aspects of community life, particularly for older adults. This topic has been explored by several studies, and they reveal the importance and challenges of these networks in rural Nigeria. Literature shows that social support provided by family, friends, and neighbors is essential for the survival and well-being of older people in rural Nigeria (Ekoh et al., 2020). However, it is worth noting that the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted these support systems. This has led to a reduction in both material support and intangible support due to limited social contact (Ekoh et al., 2020). Eboiyehi (2010) also noted that traditional support systems face challenges due to the rural-urban migration of adult children. When some migrant children send money back home to their parents, this rarely improves care for the aged within the household. As a result of this, the elderly adopt various coping strategies to sustain themselves, including reliance on aged spouses, church members, and friends. It is equally worth noting that studies have found contradictions in the effectiveness of different types of social support. While family support is traditionally considered crucial, one study found that social support from friends, rather than family, was significantly associated with good compliance with hypertension treatment in a poor urban community in southwest Nigeria (Osamor, 2015, Agu, et.al, 2021). Therefore, the nature and source of social support can affect health outcomes differently.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

a. Resilience Theory

Resilience is a dynamic and adaptive process through which communities and individuals effectively recover from stress and adversity. It involves the ability to maintain or return to stable psychological and physical functioning despite challenging life events (Lee et al., 2022; Butler et al., 2021). Various scholars have developed and expanded resilience theory, but its foundational concepts are often attributed to developmental psychologist Norman Garmezy. His research laid the groundwork for understanding resilience as a process of overcoming challenges. This theory has evolved over time with contributions from different scholars across different disciplines. Community resilience, in particular, is understood as a process connecting a network of adaptive capacities to successful adaptation after a disturbance (Norris et al., 2007). Community resilience emerges from four primary sets of adaptive capacities: Economic Development, Social Capital, Information and Communication, and Community Competence (Norris et al., 2007). The development of resilience is influenced by various factors, including internal resources (such as personality traits and coping strategies) and external support systems (Butler et al., 2021; Haraz & Danut, 2023). Interestingly, research suggests that exposure to moderate levels of stress can actually strengthen an individual's resilience through a process known as hormesis, similar to how the body builds immunity (Oshri, 2022). This highlights the dynamic nature of resilience, as it can be enhanced through experience and adaptation

Resilience Theory and Community Support

Resilience Theory posits that communities and individuals can effectively recover from stress and adversity by activating adaptive capacities. In the context of rural Nigeria, these capacities are significantly interwoven with community support systems. Social capital is a key element of community resilience, and it refers to the networks of relationships and mutual trust that facilitate collective action and support. In Nigerian communities, this is evident through strong family networks, communal ties, and religious institutions that provide emotional, practical, and spiritual resources during economic hardship. Community competence is another core concept of Resilience Theory. It refers to a community's ability to identify and address its challenges effectively. In rural Nigeria, this competence manifests in the formation of support groups, such as the 'Nsusu Groups' among widows, and the utilization of social networks to cope with adversity (Nwokoro & Ogba, 2018). These practices demonstrate the community's ability to leverage existing resources and collective agency to respond to economic pressures and promote mental well-being (Madsen et al., 2019). The concept of hormesis, or the idea that exposure to moderate levels of stress can strengthen resilience, is also relevant. In the context of rural Nigeria, where economic hardship is a recurring reality, the ability to navigate these challenges collectively, often supported by strong community bonds, can build resilience. The Idea of age grade system,"Adaora",

"Nwaora"(a child or a son/daughter is owned by all} have being a source of social support nertwork in the rural areas where by your kinsmen helps in marrying a wife and training of children. These have served as buffers to economic stress. This communal approach to weathering crises fosters a sense of shared identity and capacity for overcoming difficulties. By actively participating in social support and mutual aid networks during trying times, individuals and communities enhance their adaptability to future economic and other stressors.

b. Ecological Systems Theory

Ecological Systems Theory (EST), developed by Urie Bronfenbrenner, is a framework for understanding human development within multiple, interconnected environmental systems. This theory emphasizes the importance of studying individuals in relation to their various ecological contexts, from immediate surroundings to broader societal influences (Crawford, 2020; Neal & Neal, 2013). EST traditionally sees these systems as nested within one another. However, recent adaptations propose a 'networked' model that views ecological systems as overlapping structures connected through social interactions (Neal & Neal, 2013). This networked approach offers a more flexible and precise way to examine ecological contexts, potentially enhancing our understanding of complex developmental processes. At the microsystem level, family dynamics play a crucial role in shaping mental health resilience. Positive parenting styles, supportive family relationships, and a stable home environment contribute to better mental health outcomes (Diab et al., 2018). The mesosystem, which includes interactions between microsystems, highlights the importance of school and community involvement in building resilience, particularly for children from broken homes (Bartolo & Cefai, 2017). At the exosystem level, social support networks outside the family, such as friends and community organizations, can significantly impact mental health resilience (Hong et al., 2011; Slimmen et al., 2024).

Ecological Systems Theory and Community Support

Ecological Systems Theory (EST) offers a framework for understanding how different environmental systems interact to influence human development and mental health. In the Nigerian context, this involves analysing how various levels of the system contribute to resilience. The microsystem, which encompasses immediate environments like the family, is critical. Positive parenting styles and supportive family relationships directly contribute to better mental health outcomes (Okwuogo & Onwudiwe, 2024). The extended family structure common in rural Nigeria provides a broader network of support, which acts as a buffer during economic stress. The mesosystem, involving interactions between microsystems such as family and community, highlights the importance of community involvement in building resilience. In rural Nigeria, this involves how families, religious institutions, and community groups interact to provide a comprehensive safety net during times of hardship. Strong mesosystem connections enhance the overall support system, reinforcing community resilience. The exosystem, which includes external social support networks, highlights the role of friends, neighbors, and community organisations in promoting mental health resilience. Traditional healing practices and spiritual beliefs, deeply rooted in rural Nigerian culture, often serve as the first line of support for mental health issues. The fact that many residents perceive depression and other mental health conditions as spiritual burdens and curses leads them to seek help from traditional healers and religious leaders (Jidong et al., 2021; Okafor et al., 2024), thus utilizing the exosystem as a first source of support. This shows that the cultural framework can provide a sense of community support and spiritual coping mechanisms that are beneficial (Jidong et al., 2022). The networked model of EST also becomes crucial in this context. Rather than viewing ecological systems as strictly nested, this model sees overlapping structures connected through social interactions. This perspective allows us to see how families, religious groups, and community networks create a complex web of support that can be mobilized in times of crisis. This model recognizes that individuals exist within dynamic systems and that their interactions across different settings help shape their resilience.

IV. Community Support As A Resilience Mechanism

i. The Psychological Impact of Economic Stress in Rural Nigeria

It has been established that economic stress significantly intensifies mental health challenges, especially among vulnerable populations in rural Nigeria (Ola & Olibamoyo, 2020; Jegede et al., 1983; Onyemaechi et al., 2018). These vulnerable groups include low-income families, children, women, the elderly, and those with pre-existing mental health conditions. They all experience increased psychological toll when faced with economic hardship. This worsening of mental health issues can be understood through several key mechanisms. There is a constant sense of uncertainty occasioned by economic stress (Petitta et al., 2020). This sense of uncertainty leads to chronic stress among vulnerable populations who already have limited resources. They experience higher levels

of anxiety as they struggle to secure basic needs such as food, healthcare, shelter, and education. A level of prolonged anxiety is usually caused by the fear of not being able to meet these basic needs. This can manifest in physical symptoms like sleep disturbances, headaches, and high blood pressure. After some time, this constant state of worry significantly impacts their mental health, which increases the likelihood of developing anxiety disorders. Also, economic stress often leads to feelings of helplessness among individuals who may feel trapped in their different circumstances with no apparent way of escaping (Padilla et al., 2009). This sense of hopelessness is a significant cause of depression, which means that individuals will suffer silently, with their depression remaining untreated. The stigma associated with poverty, combined with the potential stigma surrounding mental health issues, may cause individuals to withdraw from social networks. Additionally, economic stress often strains family dynamics, especially in vulnerable households with scarce resources. Economic stress can lead to conflicts over money, which creates tension among family members. As a result of the economic stress, individuals may experience more pronounced domestic conflict, with financial stress amplifying pre-existing gender-based power dynamics and leading to domestic violence or emotional abuse. An environment such as this can contribute significantly to a toxic household atmosphere, severely impacting the mental health of all family members, including children.

Moreover, studies reveal that economic stress often drives individuals toward unhealthy coping mechanisms such as substance abuse (Vetrivel et al., 2024; Sinha, 2024 & Sinha, 2001). Alcohol and drugs may offer a temporary escape from the persistent psychological strain of economic hardship. However, these substances do not offer any lasting solution, and they can worsen underlying mental health conditions such as depression and anxiety. This maladaptive coping mechanism eventually causes more strain on the individual than the initial economic stress that led to the development of substance addiction (Okonkwo et.al, 2023). Finally, children and adolescents from economically stressed families are highly susceptible to the mental health effects of economic strain. Economic stress in the household can result in emotional neglect when parents get preoccupied with financial survival. Children who get exposed to such environments are more likely to develop anxiety, depression, and behavioral problems. Adolescents may struggle with their identity and self-worth, feeling the weight of economic pressure at an early age. This can also lead to poor academic performance and early involvement in risky behaviors, further perpetuating the cycle of poverty and mental health struggles.

ii. Traditional Support Systems in Rural Nigeria

John Mbiti used his famous "I am because we are..." to explain the African sense of personhood and identity to the world. It points to the communitarian life of the Africans. For the African, an individual's life is essentially connected to the community and social relationships. This is the philosophy that this paper proposes we tap into to enhance community well-being and individual health through the cultivation of strong resilience amidst the economic stress in Nigeria. A critical look at the family, religious institutions, and communities and their roles in rural Nigerian communities, especially, will drive this point home better. These structures play a significant role in maintaining mental health resilience and improving psychological well-being. In areas where these pillars function optimally, they support people, and in areas where they are absent or do not function optimally, the psychological health of the individuals around them is in danger. Let us briefly examine these systems and how they buffer against the diverse effects of economic hardship.

iii. Family as a Primary Support System

The family is the basic unit of the society (Stenvig, 1990; James, 1982). It is equally the basic support unit in Nigerian society, especially in rural areas where extended families often live close together (Ohaeri, 1998). During times of economic stress, the family becomes a source of emotional, financial, and psychological support. Family members share their burdens and resources to ensure the survival of each individual member of the family. In the first place, the family is a source of emotional and social support (Ohaeri, 1998). This support is not merely passive; it involves active engagement and empathy. Family members often share their worries, offer words of encouragement, and provide a listening ear. They create a space where individuals feel understood and valued. One of the distinct features of a rural Nigerian community is that a neighbour can always come visiting without prior notice. This gives room for regular interactions between members of a family and community. As such that any individual who experiences any difficulty can always approach another member of the family or community without prior notice. Regular interactions, such as shared meals and evening gatherings, are crucial in fostering a sense of togetherness and reducing feelings of isolation. This sense of togetherness is achieved when family members offer a sense of belonging and emotional comfort in times of financial crisis. It helps reduce feelings of isolation and hopelessness. Regular interactions and shared meals serve as informal counseling mechanisms that help individuals cope with financial stress and anxiety.

Beyond emotional and social support, families also offer financial and practical support (Obayan, 1995). Often, families act as a social safety net, offering emotional support and financial assistance to relatives facing severe economic hardship. It may be through direct financial aid, sharing food items, etc. Families demonstrate a remarkable capacity to pool resources during economic downturns. This is not always a formal arrangement but often an informal, flexible approach. Resources, whether they are financial, food, or other necessities, are shared to ensure the survival of each member. When a family member faces job loss or a medical emergency, others step in to provide financial assistance, share their food supplies, or offer other essential resources. The decision-making process is often guided by a sense of shared responsibility, taking a clue from the Igbo adage *bunu bunu, ibu anyi danda* (ants can carry any burden when they work in unity). This support may be limited but still can mitigate the immediate impact of financial insecurity on mental health. By offering financial and practical support, families reduce acute stressors like hunger and helplessness. In addition to the immediate support provided during economic stress, families also act as a source of motivation for their members to improve their circumstances. Research has shown that the desire to support one's family can be a powerful motivator in different contexts, such as the workplace (Onwudiwe & Nwokolo, 2024. Anazonwu et al., 2016). For example, the concept of "family motivation" suggests that employees who view their work as meaningful in serving their family and recognize that their work can meet family needs, are driven to engage in positive behaviour, and even go above and beyond in their jobs (Onwudiwe & Nwokolo, 2024). This shows that the family unit is not only a support system but also a driver for individual members to strive for betterment, which may have positive knock-on effects for the wider community.

More so, family members also offer substantial practical support to each other. This includes childcare, cooking, and household chores. This division of labor helps to alleviate the immediate pressures on individuals facing economic stress. For instance, if a mother loses her job, she can easily take her children to her sister's house so that her sister will help her with childcare, allowing her to focus on finding new employment. Similarly, families often help with farm work, ensuring that essential tasks are completed to sustain everyone in the household. Again, there is a certain level of intergenerational support that exists in rural communities where older family members play a crucial role in providing guidance and support based on their experience. They offer advice, share stories of resilience, and provide emotional stability during times of economic hardship. For instance, on moonlight nights, children and adolescents congregate at the feet of an elder who will furnish them with stories meant to grow their wisdom and resilience to face the vicissitudes of life. Younger family members, in turn, assist older members, ensuring that they are not neglected and creating a reciprocal system of support. This also serves as a mechanism to manage conflicts in situations where economic stress has introduced tensions within families. Open communication, mediation by older members, and a shared commitment to family unity are often used to resolve disagreements. Families prioritize their overall well-being and work to prevent conflicts from weakening the support system.

iv. Religious Institutions as a Support System

Religious institutions also serve as spiritual and psychological anchors in the community. In Nigeria, churches and mosques are central to rural Nigeria's spiritual and mental health spheres. Many Nigerians will tell you that faith provides a sense of purpose and a mechanism for coping with economic stress (Mahmoud et al., 2022). In the first place, religious institutions provide psychological relief by framing economic stress within a large narrative of faith, destiny, and resilience (Manning & Miles, 2017; Bradshaw & Ellison, 2010). In religious institutions, teachings emphasizing patience and endurance help individuals find meaning in their suffering. Both Christian and Islamic teachings often emphasize the importance of patience, endurance, and faith in the face of adversity. This reduces feelings of helplessness and despair. For example, messages from religious leaders may highlight the idea that economic hardship is a temporary trial sent by a higher power, providing a sense of meaning and hope. Teachings that stress the value of perseverance encourage individuals to keep striving even in the face of setbacks. Additionally, many spiritual traditions encourage reliance on prayer and meditation as a way to cope with stress and anxiety. Religious narratives also tend to highlight the importance of community and mutual support, emphasizing that individuals are not alone in their suffering and can rely on others for assistance. In this framework, economic hardship is reframed as a test of faith that can ultimately lead to spiritual growth. This approach helps individuals find solace and purpose, preventing them from becoming overwhelmed by feelings of hopelessness and despair. Again, religious gatherings such as church services and mosque prayers improve a sense of community and collective belonging. This sense of solidarity is essential in maintaining mental health resilience, as it creates a space where people feel less isolated and more connected to others in their community. They involve communal singing, prayers, and other participatory activities, fostering a feeling of shared experience and mutual support.

Yet again, they provide material support through charity initiatives. These may include food items or financial assistance to impoverished families. These initiatives are often funded by contributions from members and are managed with the aim of addressing immediate needs and fostering a sense of communal responsibility. This eases the burden of economic stress and contributes to mental well-being by directly addressing some of the economic stressors that fuel psychological distress. More so, as the elders in families offer counsel and advise to members of the family, religious leaders do likewise in the religious houses. Spiritual leaders offer counsel and guidance, often serving as the first point of contact for people struggling with mental health challenges. They are deeply rooted in the community, offering advice and support during times of economic hardship. They leverage their positions of authority to encourage resilience and provide comfort to those who are suffering. A study found that a good majority of Nigerians would meet their religious leader first when they experience any health challenge even before going to the hospital (Adegoke, 2007, Okoye, et.al 2017).

Finally, the significance of specific religious rituals in the lives of Nigerians cannot be overstated. Some of these religious rituals provide comfort and a sense of spiritual well-being. These may include prayer sessions, fasting, or other practices which offer spiritual and psychological relief during periods of economic distress. Prayer and chanting have been shown to have positive effects on mental health and emotional regulation. A randomized controlled trial found that prayer using imagination cultivates inner senses and leads to more intense spiritual experiences (Luhmann & Morgain, 2012). This could be extrapolated to be applicable to Nigerians as many Nigerian congregations pray using imagination. Similarly, chanting, both vocal and silent, resulted in significant decreases in cortisol levels and self-reported anxiety, while increasing altruism scores (Perry et al., 2023). These rituals can help people to connect with their beliefs, find solace, and strengthen their resolve during difficult times. Religious chanting has also been found to help form a positive schema to counterbalance negative emotions, as indicated by increased brain activity in regions like the amygdala, thalamus, and midbrain when viewing fearful images (Gao et al., 2020). So religious rituals in general help Nigerians more than people know.

v. Community as a Support System

The last traditional system that buffers against economic stress involves the community (Polimeni, 2006). The collective strengths of social networks serve as an important buffer against the psychological impacts systems are lacking or inadequate, the community steps in to fill the gap. The community fills the gap by offering emotional, financial, and social resources that help individuals and families cope with adversity. The importance of social support for mental well-being is further highlighted by studies focusing on specific populations, such as postpartum mothers. Research has indicated a strong correlation between low self-esteem and insufficient social support with increased rates of postpartum depression (Onyemaechi et al., 2024). These findings show that mothers with low self-esteem and inadequate social networks are significantly more likely to experience postpartum depression. This emphasizes the critical role of social connections in safeguarding mental health, particularly during vulnerable periods such as the postpartum phase. The study also found that increased social support and integration into social networks were key to improved self-appraisal and self-esteem, thus leading to better mental health outcomes (Onyemaechi et al. 2017).

In the first place, the community provides emotional solidarity in times of economic hardship. This fosters resilience through tight-knit social networks of friends, neighbors, and extended family members. This is not just about proximity; it's about actively sharing each other's burdens and providing a network of people that understand what others are going through. This connectedness helps to reduce feelings of loneliness and isolation. This often manifests in daily interactions, informal chats, and a general atmosphere of support and empathy, where individuals feel comfortable seeking help when needed. This collective problem-solving approach may involve neighbors offering food or financial assistance to families in crisis. It can also involve neighbors helping with farm work, sharing tools and equipment. This reduces the immediate financial strain on vulnerable households, lowering the psychological pressure caused by basic survival concerns. This mechanism demonstrates the long tradition of mutual aid, where individuals provide help to one another with the expectation that such assistance will be reciprocated when needed. This tradition of mutual aid is a cornerstone of community support in rural Nigeria. Individuals help each other with the expectation that such assistance will be reciprocated when needed. This system creates a social safety net that ensures community members can rely on each other during economic stress. This mutual exchange builds bonds and creates a robust social safety net. One cannot neglect the positive impact of social activities in the lives of rural Nigerians. Social activities like community festivals, gatherings, and communal work projects help foster a sense of belonging and mutual support. These events provide opportunities for people to connect, share experiences, and reinforce social bonds. They act as informal support networks, where people can find emotional relief, social connection, and practical help in challenging times. For instance, communal rituals, such as harvest festivals, often bring communities together to celebrate

the bounty of the land and reinforce a sense of collective identity and shared prosperity. These festivals typically involve traditional music, dance, and masquerade parades. They provide an outlet for emotional expression and a sense of belonging. Additionally, traditional gatherings like weddings and funerals, while solemn, provide important social support networks. It is no longer secret that Nigerians are known for their lavish wedding and funeral ceremonies (Smith, 2004; Fagbola, 2019). These events allow people to come together, share their joys and sorrows, and offer practical and emotional support to one another, reinforcing the interconnectedness of community members. These rituals and practices are not merely social events; they are mechanisms that build resilience and provide a sense of stability in challenging times.

vi. The Impact of Modernization on Traditional Support Systems

Having discussed the different mechanisms through which the rural Nigerians receive support from the community in times of economic downturn, it seems pertinent to address the challenges that these traditional support systems face. The most significant challenge to these traditional support systems is modernization. Modernization, characterized by urbanization, globalization, and shifts in socio-economic structures, is significantly impacting these traditional support systems that have historically been vital for mental health resilience in rural Nigeria. These systems, rooted in family networks, religious institutions, and communal ties, are facing both challenges and adaptations as they navigate these changing landscapes. One of the most significant impacts of modernization is the rural-urban migration of young adults seeking educational and employment opportunities. The Japa syndrome as is it commonly called often leads to the dispersal of extended families, weakening the close-knit family structures that have traditionally served as primary sources of emotional and practical support. While migrant children may send remittances back home, this financial support often does not compensate for the loss of physical presence and direct care, particularly for older family members. This can result in a decline in the intergenerational support mentioned above and a sense of isolation among those left behind in rural areas. Again, modernization and globalization also contribute to the erosion of communal ties, as individualistic values begin to take precedence over collectivist traditions. Africans have always been known by their communal nature, but the individualistic nature of the westerners is slowly and rapidly eroding the communal identity of the Africans. The increasing influence of Western culture, facilitated by media and technology, can lead to a decline in participation in communal activities and a weakening of mutual aid systems. As communities become more individualized, there is a risk that the strong social safety nets that once provided crucial support during economic hardships may diminish.

More so, while religious institutions continue to play a significant role in rural Nigeria, they also face challenges from modernization. The rise of secularism and alternative belief systems can lead to a decrease in traditional religious participation. Additionally, the increasing influence of globalized media may introduce new values that sometimes conflict with traditional religious teachings. This can diminish the role of religious institutions as a primary source of spiritual and psychological relief for some people. Another challenge is the fact that these traditional support systems are not static but dynamic despite the challenges they face. For instance, families that have geographically dispersed are using technology to stay connected, with regular calls, video chats, and social media groups maintaining ties. The adaptability would mean that the systems would not remain the same but would reach to change. Some religious institutions are also embracing technology to reach younger audiences and provide online support, adapting to changing communication preferences. Communities are finding new ways to collaborate, sometimes adopting new models of resource pooling that better suit modern economic realities. Finally, as these support systems weaken or adapt, it's important to note the potential impact on mental health. The loss of close family and community ties can increase feelings of isolation and vulnerability, especially in the face of economic stress. Individuals who are less connected to their traditional networks may have fewer coping resources, making them more susceptible to mental health challenges. This underscores the need for both preserving the positive aspects of traditional systems and integrating them with modern mental health support. While these systems are facing significant pressures from urbanization and globalization, they also demonstrate a capacity to adapt and innovate. This recognition is vital for developing effective policies and interventions that support both the strengths of traditional systems and the unique needs of modern society.

V. IMPLICATIONS

This exploration of the role community support plays in buffering the mental health impacts of economic stress in rural Nigerian communities has several implications. The discussions in the paper have several key implications for policy, mental health interventions, community-based approaches, and further research.

The first obvious implication of this paper concerns incorporating community structures into the National Mental Health Policy. The family, religious institutions, and the general community are crucial in mental health support, and policymakers should be encouraged to integrate these pillars into Nigeria's mental health strategies formally. Governments at different levels, both Federal and State, should empower health institutions to collaborate with community leaders to develop policies that leverage local support systems for mental health resilience. There is an urgent need to invest in community-driven mental health initiatives, especially in rural areas where formal services are inadequate. This investment could involve training community leaders and clergy in primary mental health first aid to improve their capacity to provide psychological support during economic downturns. It could also include awareness programs in communities to foster social connection within the different communities, as this will significantly enhance resilience and how people bounce back from the negative situations, they have found themselves in due to economic stress. Additionally, the reliance on informal community support during economic stress could be an avenue for the government to consider implementing or expanding social safety net programs that offer financial relief and healthcare subsidies to rural populations. This would reduce the psychological burden on both individuals and communities. Moreover, this paper opens new avenues for research into how specific cultural practices, such as communal rituals and spiritual teachings, serve as psychological buffers during times of economic hardship. Understanding these mechanisms more deeply is crucial and will enlighten and inform the development of community-based mental health interventions. It will also inspire further studies to assess the long-term effectiveness of community-driven mental health strategies. This includes examining how sustainable these support systems are during prolonged economic downturns and how they can be better supported by national mental health initiatives.

VI. LIMITATIONS

It is worth noting that the buffering effect of social support during economic adversity may have limitations. For instance, while social capital is positively associated with health outcomes, some research suggests that it may not consistently act as a buffer during trying economic times (Mayer, 2017). Again, while community support networks offer crucial assistance during times, acknowledge that their effectiveness can vary among individuals. The capacity to utilize and benefit from these support systems may be significantly shaped by early life experiences. Research indicates that growing-up experiences, encompassing emotional, social, and environmental factors, can substantially influence mental resilience (Okwuogo & Onwudiwe, 2024). Those who have had positive growing-up experiences that fostered self-reliance and coping skills may be more adept at leveraging community support, whilst others who have experienced adversity might need more tailored interventions (Okwuogo & Onwudiwe, 2024). Understanding the impact of such early experiences is crucial in designing effective and equitable community-based mental health initiatives that address the unique needs of all individuals, ensuring no one is left behind. Additionally, at-risk populations may experience a situation where the detrimental effects of dysfunctional networks on mental health outweigh the benefits of positive assistance (Ayala-Nunes et al., 2017).

VII. CONCLUSION

This study emphasizes the vital importance of community-based support in mitigating mental health issues stemming from economic hardship in rural Nigerian areas. In regions where professional mental health care is often unavailable, traditional support networks—including family members, religious organizations, and community elders—act as essential sources of resilience. These community-centered systems offer emotional, spiritual, and tangible assistance, enabling individuals and families to cope with the psychological impact of financial difficulties. The insights highlight the critical role of existing community networks in enhancing mental health resilience. Beyond alleviating the immediate effects of financial strain, social support systems cultivate a shared sense of identity and mutual responsibility, strengthening the community's psychological well-being. Nigeria can develop a more comprehensive mental health care strategy by combining these traditional support mechanisms with formal mental health policies and programs. This integrated approach would be better aligned with rural communities' cultural and socioeconomic context. Stabilizing these community-driven support systems will be crucial for protecting the mental well-being of at-risk groups in the face of ongoing economic difficulties in Nigeria. Decision-makers, mental health experts, and local leaders must join forces to ensure these informal networks are acknowledged, backed, and given the means to deliver practical psychological support during financial hardship. The inherent resilience found in rural communities serves as a crucial, long-lasting resource for enhancing mental health in economically disadvantaged regions of the nation.

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